

US Integrated Ocean Observing System (IOOS[®]) - Enabling Decisions, Advancing Technologies

Zdenka Willis
Director, US IOOS
NOAA
Silver Spring, MD

Abstract— The United States Integrated Ocean Observing System (IOOS[®]) is a user-driven, coordinated network of people, organizations, and technology that generate and disseminate continuous data about our coastal waters, Great Lakes, and oceans supported by strong research and development activities. IOOS[®] is our Eyes on our Oceans, Coasts and Great Lakes that enable the United States to track, predict, manage, and adapt to changes in our marine environment and deliver critical information to decision makers to improve safety, enhance our economy and protect our environment. IOOS enables decision making every day and fosters advances in science and technology. IOOS, in the United States, has been compared to the National Weather Service but an unanswered question is whether there exists an “ocean enterprise” like the weather enterprise. Technologies must be incubated and rapidly inserted to keep the US IOOS system operating effectively and efficiently. Since oceans know no boundaries, US IOOS is also the United States’ contribution to the Global Ocean Observing System which is part of the ocean contribution to the Global Earth Observation Systems of Systems (GEOSS). US IOOS is supporting the Blue Planet Initiative under GEOSS in a number of efforts.

Keywords—Ocean Observing, Ocean Enterprise, Ocean Technologies, GOOS, GEO, GEOSS

I. INTRODUCTION

So what is the Integrated Ocean Observing System (IOOS[®]) and why should the United States embark on such an endeavor. So why IOOS? In simple terms, we enable decision making every day; foster advances in science and technology. Whether you realize it or not each and every one of you relies on IOOS and we look to forge new partnerships to increase the use of every observation that is taken. To make this work, the US IOOS Program Office coordinates the ocean, coasts and Great Lakes observing efforts of Federal Agencies and links them with a network of Regional Associations (RA) and capabilities. The RAs by being part of a national program, IOOS, make them a network as opposed to a collage of observations.

You can also liken IOOS as an orchestra, but instead of instruments and beautiful symphonies we are bringing together many organizations and entities that measure and monitor the oceans coasts and Great Lakes to make informed

decisions affecting lives and livelihoods. In this paper I will provide examples of how IOOS enables the decision making process, talk about our efforts in defining the ocean enterprise in the United States and focus the importance of contributing ocean information to the global efforts such as the Global Earth Observation System (GOOS) and the Group on Earth Observations (GEO).

II. ENABLING DECISION MAKING; ADVANCING TECHNOLOGIES

IOOS is focused on making data easy to use. We have incorporated the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) standards for Sensor Observation Service (SOS) to serve our data but this is not enough because they are not specific enough therefore we have developed the IOOS recipe. I compare this to making chocolate chip cookies, each of us fondly remembers our family’s recipe and they taste great but they have “special” ingredients. Well a computer can’t deal with “special” ingredients, so we need a single recipe. IOOS has developed that single recipe for SOS and two reference software packages that allow you to use the IOOS recipe, available at <https://code.google.com/p/ioostech/>. As a result the RAs who operate Regional Data Assembly Centers (DAC) make data available from State, Local, Tribal governments, academia, industry, NGOs and often re-serve Federal data have become one-stop shops for easy data access. This then feeds into the national catalog. For example, the IOOS RA in the northeast United States – NERACOOS, provided 7.8 million observations from their assets in 2013.

So how does that translate into enabling decision making?

A. Case 1: Safe Navigation- Enabling Decisions

The United States relies on safe and efficient shipping for all aspects of our lives from clothes, to electronics to food and exported \$570 billion dollars in goods and commodities in 2011. Without ocean observations we could not safely operate these ships in US waters. NOAA’s Center for Operational Oceanographic Products and Services (CO-OPS) operates the Physical Oceanographic Real Time System (PORTS[®]). The program began in 1991 as a demonstration project in Tampa Bay, Florida, following the 1980 Sunshine Skyway Bridge accident. The accident underscored the need for real time information to provide a comprehensive situational awareness

of one's operating environment to enable best safety of life and property decisions. Just this last month, Jacksonville, FL became the 24th system in the United States. This is complemented by the work that of the IOOS RAs. For example in the Los Angeles/Long Beach area, in collaboration with the Coastal Data and Information Program (CDIP), SCCOOS is conceptualizing a new project with the Marine Exchange of Southern California to support supertankers coming into LA/Long Beach using highly specific under-keel clearance and wave information. Right now SCCOOS provides currents from the High Frequency Radar (HFR), waves from CDIP, virtual buoys, and forecasts to alert the Harbor pilots when conditions are unsafe for the large vessels to come into port. In the Northeast US, The Penobscot Bay (Maine) Pilots routinely access IOOS – NERACOOS (Northeastern Regional Association of Coastal Ocean Observing Systems) buoys, wave and wind forecasts to decide when to board ships. For example, in February 2013 the pilots encountered the situation where the seas at the pilot boarding area were 4 foot when the ship left Boston, but NERACOOS predicted 8-11 foot seas with a short period when the ship was to arrive the boarding area. The pilot cancelled the job well ahead of the vessel's arrival and rescheduled the boarding for the next day when the conditions were predicted to be better. The forecast verified and while the boarding was challenging it was done safely. Further the ability to accurately predict the seas provided the shipper with a firm idea of when his ship would dock. "The coast of Maine supports multi-million dollar fishing and tourism industries so when making decisions about bringing a 700 foot tanker full of fuel into port we need the best ocean and weather information possible, which is why we depend on IOOS buoy observations and forecasts to ensure safety and efficiency of these critical operations." Captain David Gelinas, Penobscot River and Bay Pilot.

B. Case 2: Harmful Algal Bloom Forecasts – Advancing Technologies

There are number of technologies NOAA is employing to advance the detection of Harmful Algal Blooms. One of these technologies we are trying to transition to operations is the Environmental Sample Processor (ESP). The environmental sample processor (ESP) is a biological sensor capable of measuring harmful algal bloom (HAB) species and their toxins in situ, and communicating these data to shore. The ESP can also be used to detect a variety of other planktonic organisms and some pathogens. The Monterey Bay Aquarium Research Institute (MBARI) developed the ESP, and the ESP is available commercially from

McLane Research Laboratories, Inc. Through a National Science Foundation (NSF) Major Research Instrument award to Don Anderson (WHOI), and with additional support from the Environmental Protection Agency, and the U.S. IOOS Program Office, six ESPs were purchased for use in the Gulf of Maine, along with four pressure housings, mooring hardware, and several instruments to provide contextual data. Funding from the NOAA Monitoring and Event Response for Harmful Algal Blooms (MERHAB) Research Program, part of NOAA's National Centers for Coastal Ocean Science

(NCCOS), was provided to support a phased deployment of these instruments in the Gulf of Maine that would augment state and federal monitoring programs for HAB-associated illnesses, such as paralytic shellfish poisoning and amnesic shellfish poisoning. In Fiscal Year 2013, the IOOS program under the new Marine Sensor Innovation project funded a small project to help accelerate the transition of the ESP technology to full operational use. The funding was used to expand the ESP instrument deployment in 2014 to three locations. The three ESP sensors operated from May 2nd to June 19th and is the first time we had a "fleet" of these sensors.

On the west coast of the United States, in Samish Bay, the National Marine Fisheries Science Center and NANOOS are working together to use the ESP to detect toxin-producing harmful algae such as Alexandrium, a producer of potent biotoxins that cause the potentially deadly disease paralytic shellfish poisoning, as well as fish-killing harmful algae (e.g., Heterosigma). Future research activities will expand the ability of the ESP to enable near real-time detection of bacterial species that are known human pathogens (e.g., *Vibrio parahaemolyticus*) and indicators of fecal contamination (e.g., *Bacteriodes* spp.). Like the assays currently used to detect harmful algae on the ESP, these assays are also DNA-based but they differ in that they utilize a quantitative polymerase chain reaction to quantify the number of copies of each target species present in the water. With these expanded capabilities, the ESP will be used to enhance ecological forecasting of harmful algae and pathogens. The data from ESPs in Lummi Bay and Samish Bay can be viewed on the US IOOS NANOOS data portal.

III. DEFINING THE OCEAN ENTERPRISE

IOOS has been described as the ocean/coastal complement to NOAA's National Weather Service (NWS). The weather enterprise has been valued at more than \$500 million according to the National Academies study – Fair Weather: Effective Partnerships in Weather and Climate Services (2003). Until last year there was no equivalent study of the ocean enterprise. IOOS is sponsoring a study to assess the marine technology and services industries via a contract to ERISS and the Maritime Alliance. In June 2013, we began a study to create a baseline inventory of companies classified as providers and intermediary companies. Providers are defined as those companies that provide ocean observing system infrastructure - sensor, platform and satellite system manufacturers and operators, as well as providers of cyber infrastructure, data management, software and modeling systems. Intermediary companies are those defined as adding value to IOOS outputs tailoring them for specific end-uses. At the end of year one, we identified 571 companies in the enterprise. While the statistics are still in draft, our results are comparable with studies done in the United Kingdom, where almost 50% of the companies have less than 10 employees and 82% of companies have been primary providers. So that still leaves the question – are there intermediaries that are there and we are just unaware or has this sector not yet developed and what are the barriers to their development. As would be

expected, firms are concentrated on the East and West Coasts of the Continental United States. 24% of firms were located in California, 17% in Texas, 9% in Massachusetts, 8% in Washington, and 7% in Florida. These five States account for 64% of all firms in the database. Over the next 18 months we will refine this data base and also interview companies to try to get further information about the state of the “ocean enterprise.

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A. Case Study: CODAR Ocean Sensors

IOOS has deployed a network of High Frequency Radar (HFR), with over 130 radars. These radars are operated by 30 academic institutions. Our industry partner is CODAR Ocean Sensors. The growth of IOOS and CODAR has mirrored each other.

TABLE I. CODAR AND US IOOS

Growing Together	
CODAR Ocean Sensors	US IOOS
1984: Barrick leave NOAA to form CODAR to commercialize HF radar	2002: California government: \$21 million for the “Coastal Ocean Circulation Monitoring Program” (COCMP)
1986: CODAR Ocean Sensors, Ltd. founded	2004: IOOS project based < 15 radars
1983-88: first-generation CODARs; deployed North Sea offshore oil rigs	2005-2006: Network emerges
1992: Second-generation CODARs	2008: Network reached 100
2002: 100th SeaSonde sold	2009: National Surface Currents Plan V1
2009: Rapid overseas growth	2012: Operational dollars in the IOOS budget
2014: 98% IOOS network; deployed in 30 countries	2104: More than 130 Radars

With the United States embracing HFR and transitioning this into operations, it has led to other nations deploying their own networks. CODAR’s willingness to invest with the community and sponsors research has made this a wonderful partnership. IOOS RAs are test beds for new technologies that CODAR is developing.

As part of the GEO work plan 2012-2015 we have launched the global HF radar task. We have held 2 meetings to date and have 10 countries signed up. See www.ioos.gov for more information.

IV. OPEN DATA ACCESS- GOOD FOR SCIENCE AND BUSINESS

Within the United States the policy is that all data from projects funded by the United States government must be full and open. This is the same principal in the GOOS and GEO domains.

But the United States also believes this is a good policy for scientific and economic reasons. “The more data is opened, the more it can be used, reused, repurposed and built on—in combination with other data—for everyone’s benefit. As our economy and society become more knowledge-based, data are core assets, creating value in their own right and driving social and economic innovation, growth and development.

Opening data creates social and economic value in myriad ways by:

- Reducing costs in the provision of existing services both by government and private sector (i.e. doing the same for less cost);
- Enabling new services and improved quality of services; and
- Indirectly contributing to improvements in governance and government services through improved accountability and citizen involvement, both of which engender greater trust in government.” (Guen)

Information helps drive decisions that lead to better modeling, predicting, and better support. We need Earth Observation data to make decisions that impact the whole nation. A bad environmental decision can impact lives, property and segments of the economy for years.

A. Case I: Saving a business – West Coast of the United States oyster hatcheries

In the Pacific Northwest, oyster larvae grow in the wild only in a handful of places. For oyster growers from California to Canada to succeed, hatcheries must raise larvae. In 2007, Pacific oyster larvae at Whiskey Creek, Oregon started dying en masse. The cause was determined to be increased acidity in the water. Rea time observing by systems in the hatchery itself, designed by Dr. Burke Hales, Oregon State University which the owners of Whiskey Creek dubbed as the “the Burkalator,” and buoys out the bays were deployed to understand the environmental conditions. Initially the equipment was used to determine when to draw “good” water. Conditions have now changed so that both hatcheries actually have to treat the water on a daily bases. The family that owns Whiskey Creek watch “the Burkalator” like day-traders tracking their stocks. In 2008, productivity for Whiskey Creek was at just 20 percent of its normal level; by 2010, it had risen to 70 percent. In this case observing information from both the government, bay buoys, and industry, the Burkalator, were used in open fashion to support not only Whiskey Creek but all the hatcheries in the Northwest United States.

B. Case 2: Getting ahead of an epidemic

Climate change will affect disease patterns. Billions of people might be affected, and with them potentially the viability of nations and societies. For example, Malaria is a major human health threat globally. About 3.3 billion people, half of world's population is at risk. In 2010 there were about 219 million malaria cases with an estimated 660,000 deaths.

Climate information and tools tailored for public health can help us get ahead of the curve. Days, weeks, even months of lead time are provided. The lead time provided by climate and

ocean based predictive tools and information, observations, and monitoring give us the opportunity to shift the whole scenario forward. (DaSilva, Thomson, Worral)

If the public health community and be better prepared for -- even anticipating -- the first case earlier, detection and monitoring will move up. So will laboratory confirmation when that is possible. The response can be mounted much earlier, whether through public outreach, a bed net program, or a vaccine campaign.

V. SUMMARY

US IOOS and its subscription to an open, free and timely access of data enables the enterprise to support many sectors. From weather forecasting, to the movement of commerce, to response to national hazards, to safe drinking water, safe swimming conditions, to ensuring there are oysters to enjoy, to spurring new businesses. IOOS enables our lives!

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REFERENCES

- [1] N Gruen, J Houghton, and R. Tooth, "Open for business: How open data can help the G20 growth targets,: A Lateral Economics report commissioned by Omidyar Network, June 2014
- [2] DaSilva, et al, "Evidence for practical application within a decision making framework, Medical Journal (MJ) 2004
- [3] Thomson, et al, "Evidence for using environmental monitoring," AJTMH 2005
- [4] Thomson, et all, "Evidence for using seasonal forecasting," Nature 2006.
- [5] Worral, et al, "Evidence of timing/effectiveness," THIH 2007 and 2008.